

A Brief History of Indian Science

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INTRODUCTION

To consider the history of Indian science, one must first know why most educated people know little about it. The reasons go back to the disastrous nature of the British Raj, which it is estimated cost India \$45 trillion dollars of wealth, and led to the destruction of native industry and education systems.¹ The literacy rate in India on the British watch declined from an estimated 70% to just 12% with a near-complete loss of memory of its previous condition.² Britain also foisted false narratives of history on India. The curricula that were introduced in school and college were not linked to India's own scholarly tradition so much so that Indians came to believe India had no tradition of science.

India was the world's leading nation in science before the Middle Ages. Sa'id al-Andalusi, who, in 1068 in Muslim Spain, wrote *Ṭabaqāt al-'Umam* (Categories of Nations)³ to assess the sciences of different nations, says that the sciences, particularly mathematics and astronomy, are most advanced in India (calling it the first nation). Indian technology was flourishing before the arrival of the British. Economists aver that India's share of the world economy in 1800 was nearly 25 percent and by the time the British left it had shrunk to about 2 percent.

Shipbuilding required the most advanced skills in the pre-industrial revolution age, and Abraham Parsons, a British traveler, described India's prowess in this field in 1775 thus: "Ships built at Bombay are not only as strong, but as handsome, are as well finished as ships built in any part of Europe; the timber and plank, of which they are built, so far exceeds any in Europe for durability."⁴

In some ways Indian shipbuilding technology was ahead of the European, for in the assessment by historian Dieter Schlingloff⁵: "The ancient Indian merchant ships differed from the Roman merchant ships in one respect, namely in their multiple masts. While in the entire European area the ships only possessed a single mainsail (and at best a fore-and-aft sail) right up to the late Middle Ages, in India two, and later three sails were common. Of course, the home territory of the Indian seafarers was not an inland sea like the Mediterranean, but the Indian Ocean. Hence they developed a sophisticated system of sails which in number of sails was only matched and surpassed by the explorers' ships of the 15th century."

Indian Sailing Vessels (*yānapātra*)

A three-sail ship shown in Cave 2 of Ajanta (Schlingloff, 1976)

India's textile industry, which was the best in the world, was decimated by the British. They cut off India's export markets by a variety of means. The Calico Act of 1721, intended to protect the wool and silk industries, banned most cotton cloths. The Act was repealed in 1774, but Indian textiles entering the British market faced stiff import duties, ranging from 27–59% ad valorem in 1803 to 71–85% in 1813.

When the mechanization brought about by the industrial revolution gave their own textiles a cost advantage, the British made sure that India was not provided the resources to build its own factories. As India became deindustrialized, it turned into a huge monopoly market for British products. British Raj made token investments in science and technology.

Jobs in India simply disappeared. Outside of village crafts, and sparsely staffed revenue and medical departments and schools, one could only find jobs in the army or police or as clerks working for urban enterprises. When the railway system was built by the British, the employees for a long time could only be British or Anglo-Indians.

More and more people became servants and cooks, if they could find anything. They became office seekers: any government position, even if only of the attendant in an office, was considered supremely desirable.

Nearing the end of their depredation of India, the British created national services. In 1920, India's scientific services had a total of 213 scientists of whom 195 were British!⁶

Comparing the path India chose with that of Japan, Sri Aurobindo argued that Japan embraced Western science while keeping to its spirit of the samurai, while India was compelled to abandon its own genius for the security of work in the office to serve the colonialists.⁷

This was the model that goes back to the British outpost at Fort St. George where Indians kept books or did other menial jobs. This has continued in recent times where Indian companies serve as the back office to Western companies without the ambition to make their own products. Likewise, as a consequence of a bizarre and misguided education policy over the last 70 years, Indian school and college curricula continue to present history through the colonial lens and so most Indians are largely ignorant of their scientific and cultural heritage.⁸

This essay is a broad overview of Indian science with general references so that the reader can obtain the details easily.

SOURCES OF INDIAN SCIENCE

Indian archaeology and literature provide considerable layered evidence related to the development of science and material progress. The chronological time frame for this history is provided by the archaeological record that has been traced, in an unbroken tradition, to about 8000 BCE. Prior to this date, there are records of rock paintings that are considerably older.⁹

The third millennium is characterized by a very precise system of weights and monumental architecture using cardinal directions. Indian writing (the so-called Indus script) goes back to the beginning of the third millennium BCE, but it has not yet been deciphered. However, statistical analysis shows that the later historical script called Brahmi evolved from this writing.

The earliest textual source is the Ṛgveda, which is a compilation of very ancient material. The astronomical references in the Vedic books recall events of the third or the fourth millennium BCE and earlier. The discovery that Sarasvati, the preeminent river of the Ṛgvedic times, went dry around 1900 BCE, if not earlier, suggests that portions of the Ṛgveda may be dated prior to this epoch.

Briefly, the Vedas speak of a tripartite and recursive world view.¹⁰ The universe is experienced in triples: regions of earth, space, and sky; body, breath (prāṇa), and mind; body, mind, and consciousness; past, present, and future. These triples are symbolized in the trinity of Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Maheśa. The trinity may, on in one's experience, be seen in dualities. The matter-consciousness and mind-consciousness dualities are represented in the pair of Śakti and Śiva. In the domain of human action, the orders of morality and freedom are represented by Viṣṇu and Śiva.

The outside and the inner processes are taken to be connected. All material systems go through changes with time and this includes the universe. All descriptions lead to logical paradox, and the one category transcending all oppositions is Brahman. Vedic ritual is a symbolic retelling of this conception.

LAWS AND COSMOLOGY

Vedic cosmology may be unpacked into the following seven components that help us visualize the foundations of Indian science in terms of its overarching elements and facilitates comparison with modern views:¹¹

1. *A Universe Governed by Laws and Characterized by Paradox.* The universe with matter and consciousness is governed by *ṛta* (laws). Since consciousness is not material, language cannot describe reality fully and linguistic descriptions suffer from paradox. The irreconcilable subject/object dichotomy represents complementary aspects of the same transcendental reality.¹²
2. *An Atomic World.* The conscious subject is separate from the material reality but is, nevertheless, able to direct its evolution. The universe is infinite in size and infinitely old, and other worlds beyond our solar system exist. The universe itself go through cycles of creation and destruction.¹³
3. *Relativity of Time and Space.* Time and space are created by the mind and they do not flow at the same rate for different observers.¹⁴
4. *Evolution of Life.* Humans arose at the end of a chain where the beginning was with plants and various kinds of animals.¹⁵
5. *A Science of Mind.* The inner space has its own architecture that is accessible to analysis.¹⁶
6. *Mathematical Reality.* Because physical reality is atomic, it is accessible to enumeration and mathematics.¹⁷
7. *Recursion.* The properties of the universe are mirrored across different scales as in the formula *yat piṅḍe tad brahmāṅḍe*.¹⁸

Due to recursion, the complementarity of consciousness and matter manifests itself in many dualities of experience. The world can be seen through the tropes of unity and multiplicity as well as freedom and deterministic evolution. Complementarity is associated with epistemology and ontology and perspectives are described in binary pairs: logic (Nyāya) and physics (Vaiśeṣika), cosmology (Sāṅkhya) and psychology (Yoga), and language (Mīmāṃsā) and reality (Vedānta).

The Sāṅkhya and the Yoga systems take the mind as consisting of five components: manas, ahaṁkāra, citta, buddhi, and ātman. Manas is the lower mind which collects sense impressions, and ahaṁkāra is the sense of I-ness that associates some perceptions to a subjective and personal experience, citta is the ever-altering memory bank. Once sensory impressions have been related to I-ness by ahaṁkāra, their evaluation and resulting decisions are arrived at by buddhi, the intellect.

There is evidence of the knowledge of biological cycles and awareness that there exist two fundamental rhythms in the body: the 24-hour related to the sun, and the 24 hour and 50 minute related to the period of the moon (the moon rises about 50 minutes later every day). This knowledge is not surprising since monthly rhythms, averaging 29.5 days, are reflected in the reproductive cycles of many marine plants and those of animals.

The Ṛgveda 10.90 speaks of these connections by saying that the moon was born of the mind and the sun was born of the eyes of the cosmic self:

candramā mana'so jātaḥ | cakṣoḥ sūryo' ajāyata | RV 10.90.13

The connection between the outer and the inner cosmos is seen most strikingly in the use of the number 108 in Indian literary and artistic expression. It was known that this number is the approximate distance from Earth to the sun and the moon, in sun and moon diameters, respectively.¹⁹ This number was probably obtained by taking a pole of a certain height to a distance 108 times its height and discovering that the angular size of the pole was the same as that of the sun or the moon. It is a curious fact that the diameter of the sun is also approximately 108 times the diameter of Earth.

This number of dance poses (karaṇas) given in the Nāṭya Śāstra is 108, as is the number of beads in a japamālā. The distance between the body and the inner sun is also taken to be 108, and thus there are 108 names of the gods and goddesses. The number of *marmas* (weak points) in Āyurveda is 107, because in a chain 108 units long, the number of weak points would be one less.

PHYSICAL LAWS AND MOTION

The history of Indian physics goes back to Kaṇāda (~ 600 BCE) who asserted that all that is knowable is based on motion, thus giving centrality to laws and their operational analysis in the understanding of the universe.²⁰

There are nine classes of substances: ākāśa, space, and time that are continuous; four elementary substances (or particles) called earth, air, water, and fire that are atomic; and two kinds of mind, one omnipresent and another which is the individual.

Let the basic atoms of pṛthvi, āpaḥ, tejas, and vāyu be represented by P, Ap, T, and V, respectively. Every substance is composed of these four kinds of atoms. Consider

gold in its solid form; its mass derives principally from the P atoms. When it is heated, it becomes a liquid and therefore there should be another kind of an atom already in gold which makes it possible for it to take the liquid form and this is Ap. When heated further it burns and this is when the T atom gets manifested. When heated further, it loses its mass ever so slightly, and this is due to the loss of the V atoms.

The atoms are eternal only under normal conditions, and during creation and destruction, they arise in a sequence starting with ākāśa and are absorbed in the reverse sequence at the end of the world cycle. The sequence of evolution of the elements is given as $V \rightarrow T \rightarrow Ap \rightarrow P$. The V and T atoms have little mass (since they do not exist in a substantive form), whereas P and Ap atoms have mass. This sequence also hides within it the possibility of transformation from V and T atoms that are energetic to the more massive Ap and P atoms.

Indian chemistry developed many different alkalis, acids, and metallic salts by processes of calcination and distillation, often motivated by the need to formulate medicines. Metallurgists developed efficient techniques of extraction of metals from ore.²¹

ASTRONOMY

We know quite a bit about how astronomical science evolved in India. The Yajurvedic sage Yājñavalkya knew of a ninety-five-year cycle to harmonize the motions of the sun and the moon, and he also knew that the sun's circuit was asymmetric. The second millennium BCE text Vedāṅga Jyotiṣa of Lagadha²² went beyond the earlier calendrical astronomy to develop a theory for the mean motions of the sun and the moon. An epicycle theory was used to explain planetary motions. Given the different periods of the planets, it became necessary to assume yet longer periods to harmonize their cycles. This led to the notion of mahāyugas and kalpas with periods of billions of years.

The innovations of the division of the circle into 360 parts and the zodiac into 27 nakṣatras and 12 rāśis took place first in India. The schoolbook accounts of how these innovations first emerged in Mesopotamia in the 7th century BCE and then arrived in India centuries later are incorrect because both these divisions are described in the Ṛgveda.

The Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa which was compiled soon after the Vedas says: “The sun strings these worlds [the earth, the planets, the atmosphere] to himself on a thread. This thread is the same as the wind...” This suggests a central role to the sun in defining the motions of the planets and ideas such as these must have ultimately led to the theory of expanding and shrinking epicycles.

Astronomical texts called siddhāntas begin appearing sometime in the first millennium BCE. According to the tradition there were eighteen early siddhāntas, of

which only a few have survived. Each siddhānta is an astronomical system with its own constants. The Sūrya Siddhānta speaks of the motion of planets governed by “cords of air” that bind them, which is a conception like that of the field.

The great astronomers and mathematicians include Āryabhaṭa, who took Earth to spin on its own axis and who spoke of the relativity of motion and provided outer planet orbits with respect to the sun. This work and that of Brahmagupta (b. 598) and Bhāskara (b. 1114) was passed on to Europe via the Arabs. The Kerala School with figures such as Mādhava (c. 1340–1425) and Nīlakaṇṭha (c. 1444–1545) came up with new innovations of analysis based on advanced mathematics.²³

EVOLUTION OF LIFE

The Sāṅkhya system speaks of evolution both at the levels of the individual as well as the cosmos. The Mahābhārata and the Purāṇas have material on creation and the rise of humankind. It is said that man arose at the end of a chain that began with plants and various kind of animals. In Vedic evolution the urge to evolve into higher forms is taken to be inherent in nature. A system of an evolution from inanimate to progressively higher life is assumed to be a consequence of the different proportions of the three basic attributes of the guṇas (qualities): sattva (“truth” or “transparency”), rajas (activity), and tamas (“darkness” or “inertia”). In its undeveloped state, cosmic matter has these qualities in equilibrium. As the world evolves, one or the other of these becomes preponderant in different objects or beings, giving specific character to each.

The Purāṇas (such as Viṣṇu, Garuḍa, Skanda) speak of 8.4 million species on the earth and in the oceans, which, astonishingly, turns out to be nearly identical to modern estimates.²⁴

GEOMETRY AND MATHEMATICS

Indian geometry began very early in the Vedic period in altar problems, as in the one where the circular altar is to be made equal in area to a square altar. The historian of mathematics, Abraham Seidenberg, saw the birth of geometry and mathematics in the solution of such problems.²⁵ Two aspects of the “Pythagoras” theorem are described in the texts by Baudhāyana and others. Problems are presented with their algebraic counterparts.²⁶ The solution to planetary problems led to the further development of algebraic methods.

The sign for zero within the place value decimal number system that was to revolutionize mathematics and facilitate development of technology appears to have been devised around 50 BCE to 50 CE. Indian numerals were introduced to Europe²⁷ by Fibonacci (13th century) who is now known for a sequence that was described earlier by Virahaṅka (between 600 and 800), Gopāla (prior to 1135) and Hemacandra (~1150 CE).

Nārāyaṇa Paṇḍit (14th century) showed that these numbers were a special case of the multinomial coefficients.²⁸

Bharata's Nāṭya Śāstra has results on combinatorics and discrete mathematics, and Āryabhaṭa has material on mathematics including methods to solve numerical problems effectively. Later source materials include the works of Brahmagupta, Lalla (eighth century), Mahāvīra (ninth century), Jayadeva, Śrīpati (eleventh century), Bhāskara, and Mādhava.²⁹ In particular, Mādhava's derivation and use of infinite series predated similar development in Europe, which is normally seen as the beginning of modern calculus.³⁰ Some scholars believe these ideas were carried by Jesuits from India to Europe and they eventually set in motion the Scientific Revolution.³¹

A noteworthy contribution was by the school of New Logic (Navya Nyāya) of Bengal and Bihar. At its zenith during the time of Raghunātha (1475–1550), this school developed a methodology for a precise semantic analysis of language. Navya Nyāya foreshadowed mathematical logic and there is evidence that it influenced modern machine theory.³²

GRAMMAR

Pāṇini's grammar Aṣṭādhyāyī (Eight chapters) of the fifth century BCE provides four thousand rules that describe Sanskrit completely. This grammar is acknowledged to be one of the greatest intellectual achievements of all time. The great variety of language mirrors, in many ways, the complexity of nature and, therefore, success in describing a language is as impressive as a complete theory of physics. Scholars have shown that the grammar of Pāṇini represents a universal grammatical and computing system. From this perspective, it anticipates the logical framework of modern computers.

The Aṣṭādhyāyī contains a meta-language, meta-rules, and other technical devices that make this system effectively equivalent to the most powerful computing machine. No grammar of similar power has yet been constructed for any other language. The famous American scholar Leonard Bloomfield called Panini's achievement as "one of the greatest monuments of human intelligence."

MEDICINE

Āyurveda, the Indian medicine system, is a holistic approach to health that builds upon the tripartite Vedic approach to the world. Health is maintained through a balance between three basic humors (doṣa) of wind (vāta), fire (pitta), and water (kapha). Each of these humors had five varieties. Although literally meaning "air," "bile," and "phlegm," the doṣas represented larger principles.³³

Caraka and Suśruta are two famous early physicians. According to Caraka, health and disease are not predetermined, and life may be prolonged by human effort. Suśruta defines the purpose of medicine to cure the diseases of the sick, to protect the healthy, and to prolong life. The Samhitās speak of organisms that circulate in the blood, mucus, and phlegm. In particular, the organisms in the blood that cause disease are said to be invisible. It is suggested that physical contact and sharing the same air can cause such diseases to spread. Inoculation was practiced for protection against smallpox.

Indian surgery was quite advanced. The caesarian section was known, as was plastic surgery, and bone setting reached a high degree of skill. Suśruta classified surgical operations into eight categories: incision, excision, scarification, puncturing, probing, extraction, evacuation and drainage, and suturing. Suśruta lists 101 blunt and 20 sharp instruments that were used in surgery. The medical system tells us much about the Indian approach to science. There was emphasis on observation and experimentation.

MIND AND CONSCIOUSNESS

Vedic deities represent cognitive centers.³⁴ It is asserted that parā-vidyā or ātma-vidyā (science of consciousness) cannot be described in words or design. In the Śrī-yantra, which is a representation of the cosmos, consciousness (Śiva) is shown as an infinitesimal dot in the middle.

The interaction between matter and consciousness is postulated in terms of an observation process called *dr̥ṣṭi-sṛṣṭi* (creation through observation), which is consistent with a universe governed by laws.³⁵

Indian texts assert that the phenomenon of consciousness cannot be studied directly as a material property. Their analysis of consciousness using indirect methods may very well be relevant for further progress of this question in contemporary science.

SCIENTIFIC SPECULATIONS

Indian thought is unique in the breadth and scope of its scientific speculations that are scattered within its high literature. These range from airplanes (Rāmāyaṇa) to weapons that can destroy the world (Mahābhārata), and to the most astonishing abstract ideas in the Yoga-Vāsiṣṭha.

The Mahābhārata has an account of an embryo divided into one hundred parts each becoming, after maturation in a separate pot, a healthy baby. There is also mention of a conception in one womb transferred to another. It also has a major section on battle with a space ship whose occupants wear airtight suits (Saubha Parva).

Universes defined recursively are described in the famous episode of Indra and the ants in Brahmavaivarta Purāṇa. These flights of imagination are more than a straightforward generalization of the motions of the planets into a cyclic universe.

The context of modern science fiction is clear: it is the liberation of the earlier modes of thought by the revolutionary developments of the 20th century science and technology. To understand why speculations were integrated into mainstream Indian literary tradition one must appreciate the centrality of the idea of ātman. Since creativity is seen to emerge not from the instrumentality of the mind but from the ātman, Indian science privileges imagination and abstraction at the highest level. Science is then an attempt to understand the dynamics of embodied consciousness both in outer and inner realms, and this notion is carried beyond into the aesthetic theory of *dhvani*³⁶ that posits that beauty in a creative expression is from the resonance that takes the viewer or the listener to the transcendence within.

CONCLUSIONS

India's civilization valued science and knowledge above all and created some of the most extraordinary conceptual advances. These include a cosmos with many solar like systems, the earliest astronomy, geometry, number theory, the ten-digit counting system and the symbol for zero, the idea of physical laws and invariance, the earliest formal system to describe a complex natural phenomenon (as in Pāṇini's computer program-like grammar that was not rivaled for 2,500 years), a very subtle psychology, the notion of health as harmony within the body and mind, the idea of invisible germs that cause infectious disease, immunization to prevent certain illnesses, and the notion of interrelatedness in nature.

Indian ideas have provided key notions³⁷ in the rise of modern science. But now in spite of great advances, we are unable to reconcile the sense of freedom and agency within the framework of machine-like laws, and in physical theory there is no place for the observer. Indian intuitions about the nature of consciousness and the approach to physics and psychology that privileges human agency may yet provide key clues for future advances in many frontiers of science.

NOTES

This is an expanded version of my essay titled “Science” for Stanley Wolpert’s Encyclopedia of India (Charles Scribners & Sons, 2005), and a later version that appeared in Medium. Much of this research is based on numerous journal articles that may be accessed here: https://www.academia.edu/46341155/Bh%C4%81rat%C4%AB_Bibliography

1. Chakrabarti and Patnaik (2019)
2. Dharampal (1971), Dharampal (1983), Alvares (1991)
3. al-Andalusi (1991)
4. Parsons (1808)
5. Schlingloff (1976)
6. Arnold (2000)
7. Aurobindo (1909)
8. Alvares (1991), Dharampal (1971), Kak (2016d)
9. Kak (2000), Kak (2010), Kak (2015); see also Vahia and Menon (2013)
10. Kak (2015), Kak (2016c)
11. This is a rewording of a list that appeared in Kak (2005)
12. Kak (2016d); see also Seal (1985) for original references from the texts.
13. Kak (2016a)
14. Obviously, we are not speaking here of the mathematical theory of relativity regarding an upper limit to the speed of light, yet the consideration of time acting different to different observers is quite remarkable. Thus in a story in the Bhāgavata Purāṇa (9.3.29): “Taking his daughter, Kakudmi went to Brahmā, and inquired about a husband for her. But Brahmā was at a musical performance by the Gandharvas and had not a moment to talk with him. When he was free at the end of the performance, Brahmā laughed and said to Kakudmi, ‘O King, many ages have passed while you were waiting. Those upon whom you may have decided are now gone, and so are their sons, grandsons, and other descendants.’” In the astronomical context, Āryabhaṭa speaks of the relativity of motion (see e.g. Shukla and Sarma (1976) and Kak (2016f)).
15. The Mahābhārata and the Purāṇas have material on creation and the rise of mankind. Here’s the quote from the Yoga Vāsiṣṭha: “I remember that once upon a time there was nothing on this earth, neither trees and plants, nor even mountains. For a period of eleven thousand years (four million earth years) the earth was covered by lava. Then demons (asuras) ruled the earth; they were deluded and powerful. The earth was their playground. And then for a very longtime the whole earth was covered with forests, except the polar region. Then there arose great mountains, but without any human inhabitants. For a period of ten thousand years (4 million earth years) the earth was covered with the corpses of the asuras.”
16. Kak (2002), Kak (2004), and Kak (2016b)
17. The great Vedic ritual was related to the motions of the sun and the moon (Kak, 2016e). A binary number system was used by Piṅgala to represent Vedic meters, and the structure of this number system may have helped in the invention of the sign for zero. In the idea of infinity in the Vedas, it is correctly understood that addition and subtraction of infinity from it leaves it unchanged.
18. Kak (2016c), Kak (2016d)

19. Kak (2016e)
20. Kak (2016a), Kak (2016d)
21. Ray (1909), Biswas (1986), Balasubramanian (2002)
22. Sastry (1985); Kak (2016e)
23. Shukla and Sarma (1976), Raju (2001), Ramasubramanian and Srinivas (2010)
24. See C. Mora et al., How many species are there on earth and in the ocean? PLoS Biol 9, (2011); this is a most astonishing coincidence.
25. Seidenberg (1962), Seidenberg (1978)
26. Saraswathi Amma (1979)
27. Ifrah (2000)
28. Srinivasiengar (1967), Seshadri (2010)
29. Datta and Singh (1962), Selenius (1975), Joseph (2000)
30. Joseph (2000), Pearce (2000)
31. Joseph (2000) with addition references in Kak (2018)
32. Rao and Kak (2016); also see Kak (2018)
33. Patwardhan (2012), Jaiswal et al. (2016), and Raghava Varier (2020)
34. Kak (2002)
35. In the orthodox interpretation of quantum theory, consciousness is a separate category as in Vedanta and the quantum Zeno effect is consistent with *dr̥ṣṭi-sr̥ṣṭi*.
36. See Ingalls, Masson and Patwardhan (1990)
37. See Kak (2018).

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